

Kinetics of reaction of chloroacetone with thioureas

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The second order rate constants for the reactions of chloroacetone with thiourea, phenylthiourea and *p*-substituted phenylthioureas have been evaluated in ethanol medium. The rate of reaction is first order with respect to chloroacetone and first order with respect to thioureas. The effect of substituents on the rate of reaction is also studied. Thermodynamic parameters are used to explain the nature of reaction. Possible mechanism for the reaction is suggested.

Kinetics of oxidation of thioureas by using various oxidizing agents have been studied¹. The rate constants for the reactions of thioamides² with phenyl bromides are also reported. Kinetics of condensation of phenacyl bromide with thiazolidines³ and allyl/alkyl bromides and arylthioureas/thioamides⁴ have also been reported. 2-(Substituted-amino)-4-methylthiazoles⁵ have been synthesized from chloroacetone and substituted thioureas.

We have reported the synthesis of some new thiazoles by condensing α -haloketones and thioamides/thioureas⁶. Literature survey reveals scanty information on the kinetic study of the reaction. This prompted us to undertake kinetic study of the reaction of thioureas with chloroacetone.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric study indicates that one mole of thiourea reacts with one mole of chloroacetone. The reaction rates were determined at different concentrations of thioureas by keeping concentration of chloroacetone constant (0.05 mol dm⁻³). The plot of log dc/dt against log C_{thiourea} is linear and slope of the plot is nearly one. Similarly, the rates were determined at different concentrations of chloroacetone by keeping concentration of thioureas constant (0.05 mol dm⁻³). The plot of log dc/dt against log $C_{\text{chloroacetone}}$ is also linear and slope of the plot is nearly one.

The order of reaction was also determined with respect to chloroacetone and thioureas by using van't Hoff's differential method⁷. Kinetic measurements were carried out at five different temperatures. The activation energy (E_a), determined from the slopes of Arrhenius plots of log K vs T^{-1} and other thermodynamic parameters are computed in Table 1. The entropies of activation (ΔS^*) of the condensation are all negative suggesting rigid nature of the transition state and also support the conversion of noncyclic reactants to the cyclic product. Almost equal values of free energy (ΔG^*) for all thioureas indicate that probably a similar type of mechanism prevails in all cases.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for reaction of chloroacetone with thioureas

Thiourea	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^*$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
Thiourea	43.83	41.15	157.86	92.19
Phenylthiourea	38.55	35.86	181.48	94.51
<i>p</i> -Methylphenylthiourea	58.27	55.58	123.81	95.61
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenylthiourea	62.11	59.60	98.63	90.98
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylthiourea	44.72	42.04	174.58	98.45

When the rate constants for the reactions are compared, the thiourea is found to be more reactive than the substituted phenylthioureas. This may be due to the presence of π -electron in benzene ring. When the reaction rates of phenylthiourea and substituted phenylthioureas are compared, the phenylthiourea and *p*-methylphenylthiourea show nearly the same rate constants as there is small effect of methyl group due to hyperconjugation and inductive effect. *p*-Ethoxyphenylthiourea shows higher rate of reaction because of mesomeric effect while withdrawing inductive effect of chloro group makes *p*-chlorophenylthiourea less reactive.

Table 2. Second order rate constants for reaction of chloroacetone with thioureas in ethanol medium

[Thiourea] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, temp = 323 K

Thiourea	$10^3 K \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at [chloroacetone] mol dm ⁻³			
	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02
Thiourea	7.78	7.92	7.82	7.95
Phenylthiourea	3.13	3.04	3.14	3.14
<i>p</i> -Methylphenylthiourea	3.03	3.06	3.10	2.90
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenylthiourea	3.91	4.06	3.86	3.72
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylthiourea	0.79	0.80	0.79	0.80

It is found that the order of reaction is two, first order with respect to thiourea and first order with respect to chloroacetone. The rate constants calculated from second order rate law are fairly constants (Table 2). The mechanism of reaction of chloroacetone with different thioureas is proposed in Scheme 1.

where, R = H, phenyl, *p*-methylphenyl, *p*-ethoxyphenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 1

Experimental

The kinetic measurements were carried out at different concentrations of reactants and temperatures. Chloroacetone (Fluka), sodium hydroxide, diethyl ether and phenolphthalein (all Qualigen) were used. Arylthioureas were prepared by the reported method⁸. Glass-distilled water was used. Standard solutions of thioureas and chloroacetone were prepared in absolute ethanol.

To a solution containing appropriate amount of thiourea (thermostated at particular temperature) was added a solution of chloroacetone (containing appropriate amount) at the same temperature. Aliquot (withdrawn at different time intervals) was added to a mixture of definite amount of diethyl ether and distilled water. It was shaken immediately and the aqueous layer containing thiazole hydrochloride

was titrated⁹ against standard sodium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The reaction was studied up to two half-lives.

Equal amounts of thiourea and chloroacetone were mixed under the similar experimental conditions and kept overnight. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured on crushed ice. It was extracted with ether to remove the unreacted reactants and aqueous layer, then neutralized with sodium hydroxide. The resulting white solid was crystallized from ethanol and characterized as 2-(substituted-amino)-4-methylthiazoles on the basis of the reported melting points⁶ and spectral data.

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